

MODERN ISSUES OF MANAGEMENT AND LEADERSHIP

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Annotation: *The article investigates the concept and the problem of leadership and its functions in the management system of the organization.*

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Leadership issues have been of interest to people since ancient times. However, a systematic, purposeful and broad study of leadership began only from the time of F. Taylor (Fredrick Taylor, Scientific Management), a lot of research has been carried out. However, there is still no complete agreement on what leadership is and how it should be studied.

Leadership is a type of managerial interaction based on the most effective combination of various sources of power for a given situation and aimed at encouraging people to achieve common goals. It follows from this and other definitions of leadership that leadership is a function of leader, followers, and situational variables.

The above definitions do not imply the need for leadership in any particular type of organization. We are talking about the interaction or mutual influence between people within the framework of any type of activity, and not just in political processes. "Leadership is the highest style, it is a power, it is the potential that a person has."

The basis of leadership is a specific type of management relationship, or leadership type. This is a leader-follower relationship. Historically, the leadership type of relationship arose much earlier than the "boss-subordinate" relationship that appeared and took shape during the first industrial revolution.

Starting from childhood, following the leader is perceived by everyone quite naturally. These are the parents in the family, these are the teachers at school, these are the heroes with whom young people want to associate themselves. The presence in the individual microcosm of people of the image of a leader is as old as the person himself. Most recognize the fact that leadership is identified with the presence of a relationship connected with the human psyche between the leader and his followers. The early stage of leadership management relations is characterized by the fact that one person occupies a central position in the community, while all the others are

located, as it were, on the periphery. Management is carried out through a centralized authority that prevails over the entire community. With this type of leadership, the follower spends his strength for the benefit of the group (organization) headed by the leader, without actually having any personal rights. This type of leadership relationship is called the master-slave relationship. Based on this type, the organization is able to quickly and in a short time to perform fairly difficult tasks in the least favorable conditions.

This type of leadership relationship is distinguished by the fact that followers recognize leadership as an integral part of the group (organization) only when it has proven its competence and value. The leader receives his power from the followers as they recognize him as the leader. To maintain his position, the leader must provide them with the opportunity to satisfy their needs, which cannot be achieved otherwise. In return, they satisfy the leadership's need to dominate and rise above them, as well as provide him with the necessary support in achieving organizational goals.

Failures befall leaders for various reasons, but success comes to leaders if they have enough of the same abilities and skills. A study of the work of many leaders-practitioners shows that in order to be successful, they need to have the ability to create an image of the future state of the organization and bring it to followers. Also, a successful leader is characterized by the fact that he gives his followers the appropriate rights and powers to implement the goal expressed in the vision, he can recognize his weaknesses and attract the necessary resources, including human resources, to eliminate them. In the course of studying the problem of leadership, many different definitions were proposed, from one side or another revealing the essence of this concept. The very word "leader" means "organizing", "managing". In management, a leader is a person who is able to influence individuals and groups, directing their efforts towards achieving goals. At the same time, the concepts of "leader" and "goal" are inseparable from each other.

The problem of management and leadership in enterprise management is relevant today, due to the fact that at present many organizations have managers with an extremely low level of professionalism, which leads to inefficiency of the organization. The solution to this problem will lead to the effective functioning of the organization, as well as to the emergence of such a concept as effective leadership, which consists not only in achieving goals and clearly fulfilling any tasks, but also consists in helping employees in group activities.

The impact of the leader's personal problems on the team's performance plays very great role. "Indirect education" is much stronger and more serious than direct management. The rules and values that are important for the leader become close to his subordinates - they begin to resemble their leader. If the manager has a negative attitude towards his own work, the same will happen to his subordinates. It is the leader who lays the standard of correct behavior, morality, beliefs, the standard of willpower.

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